

Multi-Scale Collision Counting for Rényi Entropy Rate Estimation

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Abstract—We present a method for estimating the Rényi 2-entropy rate h_2 of stationary ergodic sources from raw byte streams. The method expands bytes to nibbles ($\alpha = 16$), computes debiased collision probabilities $\hat{F}_2(k)$ at k -gram orders $k = 1, \dots, K$ via the falling-factorial estimator, and extracts the entropy rate from the ordinary least-squares slope of $\log \hat{F}_2(k)$ versus k . On synthetic Markov chains with known ground truth, the estimator achieves median error < 0.003 at $n = 50,000$ with $R^2 > 0.999$. On 124 DNS tunnel capture files spanning ten classes (eight tunnel tools and two benign categories), the Rényi entropy rate h_2 alone (ARI = 0.720) outperforms Shannon entropy—both single-scale (ARI = 0.246) and multi-scale slope (ARI = 0.204)—for model-free tool classification (Δ ARI = 0.516). This advantage persists after Miller-Madow debiasing of the Shannon estimator, confirming it is intrinsic to the collision probability functional rather than an artifact of estimation bias. The (h_2, h_3, h_4) multi-order fingerprint provides modest additional gain (ARI = 0.747). We additionally show that R^2 of the linear fit decreases monotonically with Markov order (orders 0–4), serving as a non-parametric memory depth diagnostic. The estimator runs in $O(nK)$ time with $O(\alpha^K)$ space. Code is available at <https://github.com/0x1Adi/renyi-entropy-rate-estimation>.

Index Terms—Rényi entropy, entropy rate, collision probability, DNS tunnel detection, anomaly classification

I. INTRODUCTION

The collision probability $F_2 = \sum_i p_i^2$, introduced by Friedman [1] as the Index of Coincidence for cryptanalysis of polyalphabetic ciphers, measures the probability that two independently drawn symbols match. It is directly related to Rényi’s 2-entropy via $H_2 = -\log_2 F_2$ [2]. Despite its century-old provenance, F_2 remains widely used: in randomness testing [3], privacy accounting [4], and streaming algorithms [5].

For sequential data, the *entropy rate* h captures the per-symbol information content accounting for temporal dependencies. Standard plug-in estimation requires $n \gg \alpha^k$ samples for k -gram frequencies to converge [6]—infeasible at byte resolution ($\alpha = 256$) beyond $k = 1$. We address this by operating at nibble resolution ($\alpha = 16$), enabling $k_{\max} = 3$ –5 at typical stream lengths ($n \geq 5,000$ bytes).

Our key finding, validated through a controlled 9-method ablation (Table II), is that the Rényi collision functional $F_2 = \sum p_i^2$ captures discriminative structure in sequential data that Shannon entropy $H_1 = -\sum p_i \log p_i$ does not, even when both are computed at identical alphabet size, identical k -gram orders, and with comparable debiasing. This is not obvious *a*

priori: both functionals are determined by the same probability vector \mathbf{p} .

Contributions. (C1) A debiased multi-scale estimator for h_2 via OLS slope of $\log \hat{F}_2(k)$, empirically validated on Markov chains (Section II). (C2) R^2 of the linear fit as a non-parametric Markov order diagnostic (Section III). (C3) A 9-method ablation isolating the source of improvement for DNS tunnel classification (Section IV).

Related work. Gecchele [7] provides an unbiased single-scale F_2 estimator but does not consider multi-scale slopes or entropy rates. Kamath and Verdú [8] provide theoretical foundations for Rényi entropy rate estimation of Markov chains. Yu et al. [9] independently apply multi-order Rényi entropies ($q = 2, 3, 4$) to CAN-bus intrusion detection—the closest methodological antecedent, though in a different domain with different estimation. Skorski [10] provides improved collision estimator analysis. Supervised methods such as GraphTunnel [11] achieve $>98\%$ accuracy on DNS tunnel detection but require labeled training data; our method requires only reference centroids with no model fitting.

II. METHOD

A. Debiased Collision Probability

Let $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_d)$ be the vector of k -gram counts from $n_k = n - k + 1$ symbols over alphabet α , where $d = \alpha^k$. The falling-factorial debiased estimator is:

$$\hat{F}_q = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^d c_i^{(q)}}{n_k^{(q)}}, \quad x^{(q)} = x(x-1) \cdots (x-q+1) \quad (1)$$

which is unbiased for the multinomial model [7].

Nibble expansion. Each byte is split into two 4-bit nibbles, giving $\alpha = 16$. This yields $k_{\max} = 3$ at $n = 5,000$ bytes (10,000 nibbles, since $16^3 = 4,096 < 10,000/2$) and $k_{\max} = 5$ for $n > 500,000$ bytes.

B. Multi-Scale Entropy Rate

For a stationary ergodic source with transition matrix P , define the Hadamard square M_2 by $(M_2)_{ij} = P_{ij}^2$. The k -gram collision probability is [12]:

$$F_2(k) = \mathbf{v}^\top M_2^{k-1} \mathbf{1}, \quad v_i = p_i^2 \quad (2)$$

TABLE I
 R^2 OF $\log \hat{F}_2(k)$ VS. k BY MARKOV ORDER (20 REPLICATES, $\alpha = 4$,
 $n = 50,000$).

Order m	R^2 (mean \pm std)	Monotonic
0	0.9999998 \pm 0.0000002	—
1	0.9999995 \pm 0.0000013	↓
2	0.9999477 \pm 0.0000177	↓
3	0.9998476 \pm 0.0000313	↓
4	0.9997505 \pm 0.0000356	↓
5	0.9997920 \pm 0.0000205	↑ (uptick)

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the all-ones vector. By Perron–Frobenius, $\log F_2(k) \approx k \log \rho(M_2) + C$ for large k , where $\rho(M_2)$ is the spectral radius. This gives:

$$h_2 = -\log_2 \rho(M_2) = -\frac{\text{slope}}{\ln 2} \quad (3)$$

where slope is the OLS coefficient of $\log \hat{F}_2(k)$ versus k .

Adaptive truncation. We set $k_{\max} = \max\{k : \alpha^k / n_k < 0.5\}$.

C. Accuracy and Convergence

We generate sequences from 15 Markov(1) chains at $\alpha \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ with 5 random transition matrices each, at sample sizes $n \in \{5,000; 20,000; 50,000\}$.

Results. At $\alpha \in \{2, 4\}$: all 30 estimates at $n = 50,000$ achieve $|\hat{h}_2 - h_2| \leq 0.025$. At $\alpha = 8$: 4/5 within 0.05; one near-degenerate matrix shows systematic overestimation (~ 0.09). Overall median absolute error at $n = 50,000$: 0.0024. $R^2 > 0.999$ for all chains.

RMSE $\times \sqrt{n}$ ranges from 0.83 to 1.49 across $n \in [500, 100,000]$, with a mild upward trend suggesting a convergence rate slightly slower than $O(1/\sqrt{n})$.

III. R^2 AS MARKOV ORDER DIAGNOSTIC

For an order- m source, $\log F_2(k)$ is exactly linear when dominated by a single eigenvalue, but sub-dominant contributions create deviations at higher orders. We generate 20 replicates of order- m chains ($m = 0, \dots, 5$) at $\alpha = 4$, $n = 50,000$, and compute R^2 of the $\log \hat{F}_2(k)$ linear fit.

R^2 decreases monotonically from order 0 to order 4 (Table I). Order 5 shows a slight uptick (0.99979 vs. 0.99975), which we attribute to k_{\max} truncation limiting visibility of higher-order nonlinearity. Orders 0 and 1 are not separable ($\Delta R^2 < 10^{-6}$). The diagnostic requires high-precision computation to distinguish adjacent orders.

IV. DNS TUNNEL CLASSIFICATION

A. Dataset

We use the GraphTunnel DNS dataset [11]: 124 pcap files spanning 10 classes (82 benign across 2 categories, 42 tunnel across 8 tools). DNS query names are extracted via `dpkt` and concatenated into a single byte stream per pcap.

TABLE II
 9-METHOD ABLATION ON 124 DNS PCAPS. ALL METHODS USE THE SAME DATA, SAME PCAP PARSING, SAME LOO NEAREST-CENTROID CLASSIFIER. METHODS 3A AND 3B CONFIRM DEBIASING IS NOT THE SOURCE OF RÉNYI’S ADVANTAGE.

#	Method	α	Dim	Type	ARI
1	Shannon H_1 byte	256	1	entropy	0.246
2	Rényi H_2 byte single	256	1	entropy	0.124
3a	Shannon rate (plug-in)	16	1	rate	0.204
3b	Shannon rate (MM debiased)	16	1	rate	0.204
4	Rényi h_2 slope	16	1	rate	0.720
5	Rényi (h_2, h_3, h_4) slope	16	3	rate	0.747
6	Shannon 3D	16	3	entropy	0.460
7	Rényi (H_2, H_3, H_4) single	256	3	entropy	0.336

B. Ablation Design

To isolate the source of classification improvement, we compare 9 methods at controlled alphabet, scale, dimensionality, and debiasing conditions (Table II). Classification uses leave-one-out nearest-centroid with Adjusted Rand Index (ARI).

C. Results and Analysis

The ablation reveals three findings:

Rényi beats Shannon at identical conditions. At $\alpha = 16$ with the same multi-scale slope method: Rényi $h_2 = 0.720$ vs. Shannon rate = 0.204 (plug-in) and 0.204 (Miller-Madow debiased). The advantage ($\Delta \text{ARI} = 0.516$) is intrinsic to the collision functional, not an estimation artifact.

Multi-scale slope is necessary but not sufficient. The slope method improves Rényi dramatically (byte single 0.124 \rightarrow nibble slope 0.720) but hurts Shannon (byte 0.246 \rightarrow nibble slope 0.204). The slope captures sequential k -gram structure, but Shannon’s logarithmic weighting dilutes the discriminative peaks that $F_2 = \sum p_i^2$ amplifies.

Multi-order adds modest gain. Adding h_3 and h_4 improves ARI from 0.720 to 0.747 (+3.7%). Shannon benefits more from added dimensions (0.204 \rightarrow 0.460), suggesting Shannon’s weakness is partly compensated by multi-scale diversity.

D. Cross-Domain: EVM Bytecodes

On 161 EVM smart contract bytecodes (118 vulnerable, 43 safe), single-scale Rényi H_2 at $\alpha = 256$ achieves Cohen’s $d = 1.32$ and AUC = 0.818. The multi-scale approach at $\alpha = 16$ gives weaker results ($d = 0.75$, AUC = 0.707) because the discriminative signal for bytecodes is compositional (opcode frequency) rather than sequential.

V. DISCUSSION

Why does F_2 beat Shannon? $F_2 = \sum p_i^2$ weights each probability by itself, amplifying high-probability k -grams. DNS tunnel tools create systematic encoding patterns (base32, base64, hex) that produce a few dominant nibble k -grams. Shannon’s $-p \log p$ weighting distributes emphasis more uniformly, diluting these peaks. The multi-scale slope then converts the amplified F_2 signal into an entropy rate that captures transition-level encoding structure.

Compositional vs. sequential signals. The choice of method depends on the data domain. For DNS (short strings, encoding structure): $\alpha = 16$ slope captures sequential nibble transitions. For EVM bytetimes (long streams, opcode distribution): $\alpha = 256$ single-scale captures compositional frequency. This suggests practitioners should select α and the slope/single-scale mode based on whether the discriminative signal is sequential or compositional.

Limitations. (1) The stationarity assumption is violated by real DNS streams with query bursts; the estimator averages over non-stationary segments without detecting regime changes. (2) R^2 cannot separate Markov order 0 from 1, and the uptick at order 5 limits the diagnostic to orders 0–4. (3) The method requires reference centroids from labeled data for classification; it is model-free but not label-free. (4) We validate on two real-world domains (DNS tunnels and EVM bytetimes). System binaries ($n = 93$), text files ($n = 2$), and crypto streams ($n = 8$ synthetic) are illustrative only and do not constitute validated applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

The OLS slope of debiased $\log \hat{F}_q(k)$ across k -gram orders provides a practical $O(nK)$ -time estimator for Rényi entropy rates, validated on synthetic Markov chains (median error < 0.003). A controlled 9-method ablation confirms that the Rényi collision functional captures discriminative sequential structure that Shannon entropy does not, achieving ARI = 0.720 vs. Shannon’s 0.204 ($\Delta = 0.516$) at identical alphabet, scale, and debiasing conditions on DNS tunnel data. Code is available at <https://github.com/Ox1Adi/renyi-entropy-rate-estimation>.

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